

ISic1282

I.Sicily inscription 1282

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tablet

Editor

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Autopsy

2017.16.11 (Liceo Lazzaro)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Probably Catania (possibly Centuripe?). The inscription was first indicated in the Museo Biscari in the second edition of Torremuzza. Kaibel, correctly, considered it to be not from Rome, due to its absence from the first edition of Torremuzza

(see Korhonen p.47). The formula is attested at Catania and especially at Centuripe. The presence of inscriptions coming from other Sicilian cities in the new material of the second edition of Torremuzza, and the entry of materials from Centuripe into the collection of Biscari at this date, might suggest a Centuripe origin, if not from Catania (all after Korhonen)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 285 + 254 + NA

Physical Description

Three joining fragments of a marble tablet, damaged upper left and below. The left and right fragments set in plaster in modern times. The rear is smooth.

Dimensions

Height 17.2 cm

Width 28.3 cm

Depth 0.5 cm

Layout

Remains of four lines of an incomplete Greek text centred on the stone

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Moderately regularly and deeply incised letters with pronounced terminal points but without substantial serifs. Broken bar alpha, lunate sigma and epsilon. Occasional use of hederæ between words. Line lower right may be remains of a supraline above a numeral.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 30 mm

Line 2: 25-34 mm

Interlineation

Line 1-2: 28 mm

Line 2-3: 15 mm

Line 3-4: 15 mm

Text

1. Θ (εοῖς) □ Κ (αταχθονίοι) ς
2. Ἀγαθόπου χρη
3. στὲ □ χα,ῖρε
4. ξ,ζ,η[σαςῆτη][---]
5. [---]

Apparatus

Text after Korhonen

Translation (en)

To the underworld spirits of Agathopos, worthy man, farewell. He lived...

Commentary

As Korhonen notes, the sigma of line 1 could either be treated as part of the abbreviation of Καταχθονίοις, or else as linguistic interference from the Latin formula D(is) M(anibus) S(acrum).

An online Italian version of this record can be found at EpiCUM514 [http://epicum.istc.cnr.it/EPICUM/?page_id=1730]

Digital identifiers:

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EDCS 39101651
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PHI 316208

Bibliography

Castelli, Gabriello Lancellotto, Principe di Torremuzza 1784. *Siciliae et objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio prolegomenis et notis illustrata, et iterum cum emendationibus, & auctariis evulgata*. Palermo. At 170 cl.14 no.5 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/501873>)

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0458 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione*. Helsinki. At 53

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum*. Berlin. At 3.5696

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezzenberger, A. 1884-1915. *Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften*. Göttingen. At 5240

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Photo J. Prag